

NUTRIENTS AND ANTI-NUTRIENTS CONTENT OF DEHULLED SOYBEAN

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ABSTRACT

The nutrient and anti-nutrient contents of dehulled soybean were investigated, using proximate composition, amino acid profile, mineral, micronutrient and anti-nutrient values. The soybean was boiled for 10 minutes, dried, dehulled and milled into a fine flour. The dehulled soybean (DSB) had high value for protein and fat (49.38 and 25.97g/100g respectively). The carbohydrate content of the DSB was very low (12.89g/100g). Leucine and glutamic acid were the most abundant essential and non-essential amino acids (6.62 and 16.25g/16g N respectively). The sulphur containing amino acids methionine and cystine were 1.22 and 2.09g/16g N respectively. The DSB is a good source of phosphorous (1193.3mg/100g). It had almost equal amount of calcium and magnesium (17.5 and 17.3 mg/100g respectively). It was a good source of thiamin (408.0mg/100g), riboflavin (394.1mg/100g) and niacin (603.0mg/100g). The DSB had very high level of trypsin inhibitor (2786.00 TIU/100g). The tannin and phytate content were 34.92 and 42.00mg/100g respectively. The dehulled soybean was found to have high nutritional values but was underscored by its high anti-nutrients; trypsin inhibitor (2786.00 TIU/100g), tannin (34.92mg/100g), phytate (42.00mg/100g), oxalate (27.62mg/100g) and saponin (34.60mg/100g).

KEYWORDS: Soybean, nutrient, anti-nutrient, amino acid, micronutrients, proximate compositions

INTRODUCTION

Soybean (*Glycine max* (L)), is a legume that grows in tropical, subtropical and temperate climate. Approximately half of the world's soybean is produced in the developing world and the other half in the developed world (IITA 2002). Soybean is an important source of inexpensive and high quality protein and oil (Khalid *et al*; 2008). Extensive works have been reported on the nutrients and anti-nutrients content of soybean but none on the quantity of the anti-nutrients content of dehulled soybean..

Soybean nutritionally emerged as one single food crop with nutrients content almost equal to that of animal product. It contains all the essential amino acids and is an excellent source of dietary fiber. Messina (2004) reported that soybean was relatively high in iron, phosphorous, copper, magnesium and manganese. Soybean contains very little starch and about half of the total polysaccharides is composed of oligosaccharides

It also contains several phytochemicals such as lectins, (hemagglutinins), phytosterols, phytic acid, saponin, protease inhibitors, a variety of phenolic acids and importantly isoflavones in relatively high amount (Messina, 2004). These anti-nutrients are compounds with adverse nutritional and physiologic effects. In animal model, protease inhibitors have been shown to cause growth retardation and enhanced chemically induced pancreatic cancer (Messina, 2004). Most of the interest in these phytochemicals focused on their possible anti-nutrient effects especially the protease inhibitors and phytic acid.

This work was undertaken to establish quantitatively the nutrients and anti-nutrients content of the dehulled soybean.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Soybean (*Glycine max* (L)) was purchased from Jos Main Market, manually cleaned to remove foreign materials. Four hundred grains of raw soybean was placed in 10 litres of boiling water containing 5.0g sodium bicarbonate. The soybean was boiled for 10 minutes and the water drained off. It was dried in the oven at 80°C for 24h and dehulled mechanically using laboratory hammer mill. It was milled in a laboratory hammer mill into a fine flour (300µm mesh screen) and packaged in a labeled low density polyethylene bag. The bag was placed in a plastic bucket with cover and stored in a deep freezer at - 18°C for analysis.

Proximate Composition

Proximate analysis was carried out on the dehulled soybean by the methods of Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC, 1980).

Determination of Amino Acid Profile

The amino acid profile of the dehulled soybean, was determined using the method by (Spackman *et al*; 1958). The sample was defatted by weighing 5g of the sample into extraction thimble. The fat was extracted with chloroform and methanol mixture (2:1) using the soxhlet extraction apparatus as described by AOAC, (1980). Two hundred milligram of the fat free sample was weighed into a glass ampoule. Seven millilitre of hydrochloric acid was added and oxygen was expelled by passing nitrogen gas through the solution. This was to avoid possibility of oxidation of cystine and methionine (Benitez, 1989). The glass ampoule was then sealed with Bunsen burner flame. The ampoule and its contents was hydrolysed in an oven at 105°C for 22 hours. Immediately after cooling, it was filtered through non-absorbent cotton wool. The filtrate was dried at 40°C using Heidolyph evaporator (Model W1). The amino acids in the flask was diluted with 5ml of sodium citrate buffer (PH 2.0). About 5 to 10 microlitre was loaded into the cartridge of Technicon Sequential Multi-sample amino-acid analyzer (TSM). Precise amounts of ninhydrin and hydrazine sulphate reagents were combined on the manifold of the TSM to form hydrin dantin. A segmented reagent stream flowed under each analyzer column to join with the eluting buffers. The stream carrying the amino acid reagent mixture went through a heating bath where development of the colour reaction product occurs. The absorbance was proportional to the concentration of each amino acid and was measured by colorimeter. The determination was done in triplicate.

Elemental Determination

The levels of selenium, zinc, iron, copper, molybdenum, calcium, magnesium, manganese, and lead in the dehulled soybean, were determined by the method of Atomic Absorption spectrophotometric method of Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC, 1980). One gram of the sample was accurately weighed and ashed for 2h at 500°C and allowed to cool. The ash was made wet with 10 drops of distilled water and 3-4ml HNO₃ (1+1). Excess HNO₃ was evaporated. The content was ashed for additional 1h at 500°C. It was dissolved in 10ml NHCl (1+1) and made up to 50ml. The mixture was forced into the flame with sufficiently high temperature to cause the atomization of the analyte element.

Total phosphate content was determined by the modified method of Fiske and Subbarow, (1935). One gram of the sample was digested with 5ml of a mixture of nitric acid, perchloric acid and sulphuric acid in the ratio 4:1:1 v/v in a micro Kjeldahi flask. The absorbance of the blue colour produced was read at 720nm.

The iodine determination was by the method of Muir and Lambert, (1973). Sodium thiosulphate (thiosulphate vi) reacted with iodine to produce sodium iodide and sodium tetrathionate. The free iodine produced a deep blue colouration which disappeared as soon as sufficient thiosulphate was added to react with all the iodine.

Vitamins Determination

Determination of various vitamins in the sample were done in accordance with the methods of the following authors : vitamin A (Pearson, 1976) ,thiamin and riboflavin (Stroebecker and Henning, 1965), niacin (AOAC,1980) and vitamin C (Roe and Kuether, 1943).

Determination of Anti-nutrients

The levels of phytates, trypsin inhibitor, oxalate, tannin and saponin were determined in the dehulled soybean.

Phytic acid (inositol hexaphosphate) content of the sample was determined by the modified method of McCance and Widdowson ,(1935).Ten grams of the sampel was extracted in 200ml of 1NHCl for 12h at room temperature. Fifty milliliters of 1% ferric chloride in 1NHCl was added and boiled. This procedure precipitated phytic acid as ferric phytate. The concentration of phytic phosphate was calculated from the standard inorganic phosphate curve prepared.

Trypsin inhibitor activity (TIA) was estimated essentially according to the method Kakade *et al*, (1974), except that 2.0g of the finely ground sample was extracted with 10ml 0.01 NaOH for 1h. Five milliliter of BAPNA (benzoyl-DL arginine-p-nitro anilide hydrochloride) solution was hydrolyzed with 2ml of 0.2mg/ml trypsin (Sigma Type 11) in 0.0001MHCl. P-nitro anilide was released as a coloured product and absorbance read at 410 nm.

The total oxalic acid content of the sample was determined by the modified method of Abeza *et al*, (1968). Two grams of the sample was digested for 1h with 10ml of 6M of hydrochloric acid. The digest was boiled and filtered. The precipitate was dissolved in 5ml of 1:4 sulphuric acid. The resultant solution was titrated against 0.05KMNO₄ untill the pink colour persisted for one minute. A blank was run along with the test sample.

The tannic acid content of the sample was determined colorimetrically by the method of Price and Bulter,(1977).Two grams of the sample was mixed with 10ml of 2MHCl. The content was shaken and made up to 50ml and filtered. Five milliliters of the filtrate was mixed with 3ml of 0.1MFeCl₃ in 0.1NHCl and 3ml of 0.008M potassium ferrocynide (K₃Fe(CN)₆). Absorbance was read at 720 nm.

Saponin was determined according to the method of Birk *et al* (1963), modified by Hudson and El-Difrawi, (1979). Ten grams of the sample was mixed in 20ml of 20% aqueous ethanol and filtered. The residue was re-extracted with 20ml of 20% aqueous ethanol. The aqueous layer was recovered while the ether layer was discarded. The process was continued until a colourless aqueous extract was obtained. The extract was washed and evaporated to dryness to obtain crude saponin.

The mean and standard error of the mean were calculated using the procedure of Steel and Torrie, (1960).

RESULTS

The proximate composition of the dehulled soybean is presented in Table 1. The dehulled soybean had 3.7g/100g moisture and 3.99g/100g ash. Soybean is an oil seed as such it had high fat value (25.97g/100g). It had fibre and protein values for 4.06 and 49.38g/100g respectively. The carbohydrate content of soybean was very low (12.89g/00g).

Table 2 shows the amino acid profile of the dehulled soybean. Seventeen amino acids were detected. The DSB was a source of nine essential amino acids. Leucine and glutamic acid were the most abundant essential and non-essential amino acids with values 6.62 and 16.25g/16g N respectively. The sulphur containing amino acids, methionine and cystine were 1.22 and 2.09g/16gN respectively.

The minerals and micronutrients content of dehulled soybean are presented in Table 3. The dehulled soybean is a good source of phosphorous (1193.3mg/100g) and calcium (17.5mg/100g). It had almost equal

amount of calcium and magnesium (17.5 and 17.3mg/100g respectively). The zinc and iron concentrations were 8.4 and 9.3mg/100g respectively. Molybdenum was found in traces in the dehulled soybean. Selenium and iodine concentrations were 0.08 and 0.27mg/100g respectively. Manganese content in the dehulled soybean was low (0.057mg/100g) while lead was not detected. The DSB was a good source of thiamin, riboflavin and niacin (408.0, 394.1 and 603.0mg/100g respectively). The vitamin A content was 5.9 RE.

Table 4 shows the anti-nutrients content of dehulled soybean. The DSB had a very high level of trypsin inhibitor (2786.00 TIU/100g). The tannin and phytate content were 34.92 and 42.00mg/100g respectively. The oxalate and saponin content were 27.62 and 34.60mg/100g respectively.

DISCUSSION

The proximate composition results of the DSB in Table 1 differed from the USAID (1986) results; moisture 8.54, ash 4.87, fat 19.94, fibre 4.96, protein 36.49 and carbohydrate 30.16g/100g. The results (Table I) revealed higher values for moisture, ash, fibre and carbohydrate but lower values for fat and protein. This could be attributed to the effects of absence of seed coat of the soybean. The lower carbohydrate but higher fat values confirmed the report of Mayer *et al* (1960) that during the maturation of many oil seeds an increase in oil content occurs concurrently with a decrease in the quantity of carbohydrate. This indicated that its carbohydrate could have been converted to fat. The lower moisture for the dehulled soybean supported the higher fat value because high fat products have low moisture and high protein.

The results presented in table 2 differed from the Lathia and Kruchten (1996) results; histidine 28, isoleucine 50, leucine 85, lysine 70, methionine + cystine 28, phenylalanine + tyrosine 88, threonine 42, tryptophan 14 and valine 53mg/g protein but similar to the FAO (1973) patterns. This is a confirmation of the statement by Messina 2004, that soybean nutritionally emerged as one single food crop with nutrients content almost equal to animal product.

Khalid *et al*: (2008) reports on the minerals and micronutrients content of soybean, Ca 225, Cu 0.75, Fe 6.90, Mg 200, Mn 2.20, K 1190, Na 9.42 and Zn 1.65mg/100g were higher than the results presented in Table 3. In the present study the dehulled soybean had higher phosphorous value. This agreed with the reports of Linder (1997), which stated that phosphorous is generally abundant in foods with high protein content. Berk (1992) reported that the major mineral constituents of soybean were mainly potassium, calcium and magnesium and the trace elements (iron, zinc and copper) were the minor constituents. The traces of molybdenum in the dehulled soybean could be attributed to adverse of anti-nutrients and food toxicants (phytate, tannin, oxalate, cyanide and heamagglutinin).

A lot of works have been published on anti-nutrients content of soybean but none on the quantity of each anti-nutrient e.g. Rackis *et al* (2004), Hunter (2001) and Berk (1992) reported generally on the anti-nutrients content of soybean but this study quantified each anti-nutrient as shown in Table 4. The phytate value of the DSB was 42mg/100g. This organic acid is present in the bran or hull of all seeds and legumes but no seed has higher level of phytate which soybean has. Phytate blocks the body's uptake of essential minerals like magnesium, calcium, iron and especially zinc (Ice, 2000). The trypsin inhibitor of the dehulled soybean was 2786.00 TIU. This is a potent enzyme – inhibitor which blocks uptake of trypsin and other enzymes which the body needs for protein digestion.

In conclusion the DSB was found to have excellent nutritional values like that of animal product but was underscored by its high anti-nutrient values; trypsin inhibitor (2786.00 TIU/100g), tannin (34.92mg/100g), phytate (42.00mg/100g) oxalate (27.62mg/100g) and saponin (34.60g/100g). Based on the above results soybean is a good, cheap source of nutrients but under scored by its high anti-nutrients content.

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Table 1: Proximate composition of dehulled soybean (g/100g, DRY WT)

Parameters	Values
Moisture	3,70 ± 0.15
Total ash	3.99 ± 0.72
Crude fat	25.97 ± 0.35
Crude fibre	4.06 ± 0.11
Crude protein	49.38 ± 0.26
Nitrogen free extract	12.89

Values are means ± standard deviation of triplicate determinations.

Table 2: Amino Acid Profile of dehulled Soybean (g/16gN

Amino Acid	g/6gN	FAO Reference Protein (1973)
Lysine	5.59 ± 0.01	4.2
Histidine	2.17 ± 0.001	
Arginine	6.33 ± 0.3	
Aspartic	7.97 ± 0.4	
Threonine	3.15 ± 0.1	2.8
Serine	4.25 ± 0.1	
Proline	3.18 ± 0.18	
Alanine	4.25 ± 0.01	4.2
Valine	3.69 ± 0.01	
Cystine	2.09 ± 0.01	
Methionine	1.22 ± 0.22	2.2
Isoleucine	4.13 ± 0.1	4.2
Leucine	6.62 ± 0.2	4.2
Tyrosine	2.76 ± 0.04	
Phylalanine	4.76 ± 0.1	2.8
Glycine	3.25 ± 0.3	
Glutamic acid	16.25 ± 0.7	

Values are ± standard deviation of triplicate determinations.

Table 3: Mineral and Micronutrients content of dehulled soybean (mg/100g, DRY WT.)

Parameters	Values
Calcium	17.5 ± 0.40
Magnesium	17.3 ± 0.20
Copper	1.1 ± 0.10
Molybdenum	Traces
Zinc	8.4 ± 0.2
Iron	9.3 ± 0.2
Phosphorus	1193.3 ± 1.78
Selenium	0.08 ± 0.0
Iodine	0.27 ± 0.0
Manganese	0.057 ± 0.0
Lead	N.D.
Vitamin A (RE)	5.9 ± 0.26
Thiamin	408.6 ± 5.6
Riboflavin	394.1 ± 34.8
Niacin	603.0 ± 13.54
Ascorbate	2.4 ± 0.08

Values are means ± standard deviation of triplicate determinations,
N.D = Not detected

Table 4: Anti-nutrients content of dehulled soybean (TIU and mg/100g DRY WT)

Parameter	Value
Trypsin inhibitor (TIU/100g)	2786.00 ± 06
Tannins (mg/100g)	34.92 ± 6.5
Phytate (mg/100g)	42.00 ± 7.5
Oxalate (mg/100g)	27.62 ± 0 2.3
Saponin (mg/100g)	34.60 ± 0 5.6

Values are means ± standard deviations of triplicate determination

Received for Publication: 03/06/2010

Accepted for Publication: 20/07/2010